

Supplementary information for Amenity complexity and urban locations of socio-economic mixing

Sándor Juhász ^{3,4},
Gergely Mónus ^{2,3,5}

¹Complexity Science Hub Vienna, Vienna, Austria

²NETI Lab, Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest, Hungary

³ANET Lab, ELKH Center for Economic and Regional Sciences, Budapest, Hungary

⁴Center for Collective Learning, Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest, Hungary

⁵Inst. for Data Analytics and Information Systems, Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest, Hungary

*Corresponding author: juhasz@csh.ac.at

1 Mobility data preparation

Our GPS based mobility data is provided by a data aggregator company that collects and combines anonymous location data from users' smartphone applications. The sample we use for our analysis is an unbalanced panel of GPS pings from 5.2 million devices in Hungary between 2019 June and 2021 May. Our raw data consists of a device identifier, a time stamp, a latitude, and a longitude coordinate, where GPS pings occur. Pings are logged in case an application on a device requests location information. Sometimes this is the result of an active behavior such as using a navigation application or requesting local weather information. In other cases, pings could be the result of an application requesting information while running in the background. As a consequence, pings occur at irregular intervals. To identify visitation patterns such as home, work or third place visits to urban locations, we transform and filter our raw GPS trajectory data in several steps. We detail these steps in the following.

As the data contains some pings attributed to the same device that indicate unreasonable behavior, we start by iteratively removing all ping pairs that signal a movement over 300 kilometers per hour speed. Additionally, we discard all devices that have fewer than 20 pings remaining after this initial speed-based filter. These two steps reduce the total ping count from 3.18 billion to 3.13 billion and the total unique device count from 5.2 million to 1.88 million.

To focus on locations where devices stopped for some time, we run the Infostop stop detection algorithm (Aslak and Alessandretti 2020). In short, it classifies GPS pings to trips or stays and clusters stationary points into stops in an effective way. We apply the algorithm with the following parameter set. $r1$, the maximum roaming distance allowed for two pings within the same stay is set to 370 meters. $r2$, the typical distance between two stays in the same destination is set to 140

meters. t_{min} , the minimum duration of a stay is set to 270 seconds, while t_{max} , the maximum time difference between two consecutive pings to be considered within the same stay is set to 7200 seconds. The minimum number of GPS pings required for stationary points is set to 2.

The parameters are calibrated using the Google location history data of 7 consenting individuals from Budapest, Hungary. We ran our stop detection algorithm on the sample trajectories with a wide range of parameters. We compared the results of the stop detection process to the personal, anecdotal experiences and to the semantic stop detection extracted from Google accounts. This experiment confirmed that the stop detection algorithm and the parameters produce a reasonable set of trips, stays, and destinations. Moreover, the subsequent home and work detection process built on it produced accurate results for our small sample.

Using the output of the stop detection process, we further filter the data to devices that have at least 2 unique destinations with over 4 different stays in each. This reduces the total stop count from 100 million to about 80 million, and the unique device count from 1.75 million to about 240.000. However, even in this final form, over 2.1 billion pings are used from the original 3.18 billion. Our empirical exercise in the end only uses information for each month from devices with identified home, work and at least a single visited third place inside Budapest.

2 Socio-economic status from census tract level real estate prices

We infer on the socio-economic status of individuals living in Budapest by connecting their identified home location to residential real estate prices at the census tract level. Approximating socio-economic status through real estate prices has several benefits in comparison to the prevalent solution of using household income statistics of urban locations. First, real estate prices are by definition connected to places, while it is harder to connect income to locations. Second, real estate statistics in the census are comprehensive, while income information only reflects on the status of active employees.

The Hungarian Central Statistical Office collects data on all residential real estate sales contracts and derives information on transaction prices for the entire country. As not every real estate is on the market and observed contracts sometimes suffer from missing information on the parameters of given properties, direct measurement on lower geographical level is difficult. By utilizing the fact that real estate prices tend to follow a strong multi-level hierarchy as location (and especially neighborhoods in Budapest) explains much of the price differences, we train a multi-level random slope regression model on the observed transaction prices (Chi et al. 2021; Snijders and Bosker 2011). To do so, we use real estate transaction contracts between 2013 and 2019. We create a pooled setting by correcting prices through the city level house price index published yearly by the National Bank of Hungary. Our model can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}h_{i,j} &= \beta_{0,j} + \beta_{1,j}s_{i,j} + \varepsilon_{i,j} \\ \beta_{0,j} &= \beta_0 + n_{0,j} \\ \beta_{1,j} &= \beta_1 + n_{1,j}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Here $h_{i,j}$ is the logarithm of the individual price of real estate i in neighborhood j . $\beta_{0,j}$ represents how much the estimated mean house price differs by neighborhoods. Estimated mean neighborhood prices are decomposed to β_0 , the city level mean, and $n_{0,j}$, the neighborhood deviation from this value. To be able to capture differences within neighborhoods, we apply the individual level parameter $s_{i,j}$ that refers to the size (floor area) of real estate i in neighborhood j . Since the effect of floor area can vary between neighborhoods, we train a random slope model. $\beta_{1,j}$ represents the effect of floor area in neighborhood j . $\beta_{1,j}$ is decomposed to a city level slope β_1 , and the deviation of neighborhood slopes around this value $n_{1,j}$.

Utilizing this model, we predict prices for every real estate captured by the last Hungarian census in 2010. By taking the mean of the predicted real estate prices at the census tract level, we get a highly granular socio-economic status map for the entire city of Budapest. Figure S1A illustrates the predicted prices aggregated to the census tract level on the map of Budapest, while Figure S1B shows the distribution of predicted real estate prices.

A

Figure S1: Predicted real estate prices at the census tract level around Budapest (A) and the distribution of real estate prices aggregated to the census tract level in Budapest (B)

3 Urban neighborhoods of Budapest, Hungary

We use urban neighborhoods as geographic units to construct our amenity complexity measures. Budapest consists of 207 urban neighborhoods and their place in the spatial scale hierarchy is between districts and census tracts in terms of area and population. The unequal size distribution of urban neighborhoods are illustrated in Figure S2 and Figure S3. The correlation between population of urban neighborhoods and the number of census tracts per urban neighborhoods is strong as Pearson's R is 0.979. Further details about neighborhoods can be found at the website of Hungarian Central Statistical Office 2022.

Figure S2: Population of urban neighborhoods based on the census of 2010 on the map of Budapest (A) and as a distribution plot (B).

Figure S3: Number of census tracts per urban neighborhood based on the census of 2010 on the map of Budapest (A) and as a distribution plot(B).

4 Alternative specifications to construct amenity complexity measures

To construct our amenity complexity measures, we create a neighborhood-amenity category matrix, where we consider every neighborhood in Budapest with at least 2 amenity categories with minimum 2 POIs. The minimum 2 POIs threshold is implemented to reduce noise in our data. We use this matrix to measure the revealed comparative advantage (RCA) of neighborhoods in amenity categories and transform it to a binary specialization matrix (M) for the calculation of complexity values at the level of neighborhoods and amenity categories, as described in the main text. Figure S4 presents how the composition of M would change in case we use alternative thresholds for minimum number of POIs per amenity categories in neighborhoods.

Figure S4: Stability of RCA values in the binary specialization matrix (M) by different specifications. (A) Changes in RCA 0/1 values in case we consider every amenity category in each neighborhood with at least 1 POI. (B) Changes in RCA 0/1 values in case we increase the minimum number of POIs per amenity category in neighborhoods from 2 to 3. (C) Changes in RCA 0/1 values in case we increase the minimum number of POIs per amenity category in neighborhoods from 2 to 5.

Figure S5: Correlation tables for (A) neighborhood complexity and (B) amenity complexity values created by applying different minimum thresholds on the number of POIs in the neighborhood-amenity category matrix.

	Coefficient of variation		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Neighborhood complexity	0.125*** (0.036)		
Neighborhood complexity min 3 POIs		0.133*** (0.045)	
Neighborhood complexity min 5 POIs			0.098** (0.039)
Centrality of location	0.089*** (0.028)	0.102*** (0.028)	0.117*** (0.027)
Population (log)	-0.050** (0.022)	-0.031 (0.023)	-0.021 (0.023)
Nr visitors (log)	0.039 (0.029)	0.037 (0.029)	0.040 (0.029)
Nr POIs (log)	0.006 (0.023)	-0.039 (0.025)	-0.052* (0.028)
Constant	0.363*** (0.057)	0.394*** (0.055)	0.396*** (0.055)
Observations	186	184	177
R ²	0.303	0.275	0.255
Adjusted R ²	0.284	0.255	0.233
Note:	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table S1: Controlled correlations between the diversity of visitors and the complexity of neighborhoods (in February 2020) in cases we apply different minimum thresholds for the number of POIs considered in the neighborhood-amenity category matrix.

Despite the different thresholds, around 90% of the neighborhood-amenity category matrix is classified by the same 0/1 RCA value. This suggests that matrix M is relative stable for smaller changes in the minimum number of POIs considered. In case we do not introduce any threshold to construct the matrix M , we classify slightly more neighborhood-amenity category with RCA=1.

Figure S5 presents the correlation tables for neighborhood and amenity complexity values based on different minimum thresholds on the number of POIs. The tables suggest that there is a clear difference in complexity values in case we introduce a minimum threshold and in case we do not. Without any noise filtering the resulted complexity values have a negative correlation to complexity values constructed from neighborhood-amenity pairs with at least 2 POIs. We opt to choose the minimum 2 POIs threshold as it results in intuitive complexity values for both neigh-

	Coefficient of variation		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Amenity complexity	0.069*** (0.016)		
Amenity complexity min 3 POIs		0.077*** (0.020)	
Amenity complexity min 5 POIs			0.094*** (0.030)
Centrality of location	0.116*** (0.011)	0.118*** (0.011)	0.116*** (0.011)
Nr POIs in category (log)	-0.006 (0.007)	0.012 (0.009)	0.022* (0.012)
Nr visitors (log)	0.069*** (0.008)	0.067*** (0.008)	0.067*** (0.008)
Constant	0.172*** (0.030)	0.121*** (0.036)	0.094** (0.045)
Observations	2,742	2,740	2,739
R ²	0.108	0.107	0.108
Adjusted R ²	0.106	0.106	0.106
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table S2: Controlled correlations between the diversity of visitors and the complexity of amenities (in February 2020) in cases we apply different minimum thresholds for the number of POIs considered in the neighborhood-amenity category matrix.

neighborhoods and amenity categories, but still not too restrictive. Table S1 and Table S2 presents that our main results are not influenced by increasing the minimum 2 POIs threshold to minimum 3 or 5 POIs.

As an alternative specification, we constructed neighborhood and amenity complexity measures based only on POIs that attract visitors along the 24 month long observed period. Figure S6 illustrates the stability of RCA 0/1 values in case we only consider POIs around Budapest visited by at least 1 or at least 10 devices during the 24 months. The figure suggests that 94% of all neighborhood-amenity pairs are classified by the same RCA value even in case we consider the attraction of POIs at the beginning of the complexity measure generation. Changing from 1 to 10 minimum visitor devices to POIs does not change the classification results. Figure S7 presents strong correlations between neighborhood and amenity complexity values based on the different settings. Table S3 and Table S4 presents that our main results remain the same even in case we build our complexity measures on POIs that actually attract visitors.

Figure S6: Stability of RCA values in the binary specialization matrix (M) in case we only consider POIs (A) visited by at least 1 device, (B) visited by at least 10 devices during the observed 24 months.

Figure S7: Correlation tables for (A) neighborhood complexity and (B) amenity complexity values created from the neighborhood-amenity category matrix where all POIs, visited POIs or POIs with at least 10 visitor devices during the observed 24 months are considered.

	Coefficient of variation		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Neighborhood complexity	0.125*** (0.036)		
Neighborhood complexity visited POIs		0.102*** (0.039)	
Neighborhood complexity POIs with min 10 visitors			0.101** (0.041)
Centrality of location	0.089*** (0.028)	0.107*** (0.028)	0.107*** (0.028)
Population (log)	-0.050** (0.022)	-0.044* (0.023)	-0.039 (0.024)
Nr visitors (log)	0.039 (0.029)	0.026 (0.030)	0.029 (0.030)
Nr POIs (log)	0.006 (0.023)	0.006 (0.023)	-0.007 (0.023)
Constant	0.363*** (0.057)	0.380*** (0.059)	0.379*** (0.059)
Observations	186	182	181
R ²	0.303	0.281	0.267
Adjusted R ²	0.284	0.261	0.247
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table S3: Controlled correlations between the diversity of visitors and the complexity of neighborhoods (in 2020 February) in case we consider POIs with visitors for the neighborhood complexity measurement.

	Coefficient of variation		
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Amenity complexity	0.069*** (0.016)		
Amenity complexity visited POIs		0.075*** (0.017)	
Amenity complexity POIs with min 10 visitors			0.075*** (0.018)
Centrality of location	0.116*** (0.011)	0.115*** (0.011)	0.115*** (0.011)
Population (log)	-0.006 (0.007)	0.001 (0.007)	0.004 (0.008)
Nr visitors (log)	0.069*** (0.008)	0.069*** (0.007)	0.070*** (0.007)
Nr POIs (log)	0.172*** (0.030)	0.154*** (0.030)	0.148*** (0.031)
Observations	2,742	2,742	2,742
R ²	0.108	0.108	0.108
Adjusted R ²	0.106	0.106	0.106
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table S4: Controlled correlations between the diversity of visitors and the complexity of amenities (in 2020 February) in case we consider POIs with visitors for the amenity complexity measurement.

5 Similarity of amenities based on their co-location

Figure S8 presents an alternative, clustered version of the $M_{aa'}$ amenity-amenity similarity matrix, which we use to construct our amenity complexity measure. The strongest stand-alone clusters consist of ubiquitous amenities such as Grocery or supermarket and Convenience store, which co-occur in many neighborhoods with a concentration of $RCA \geq 1$. A normalized version of this matrix is often represented as a network, similarly to the product space or the knowledge space Hidalgo 2021. Figure S9 illustrates our amenity-amenity similarity matrix as a network with non-normalized edge weights.

Figure S8: Clustered version of the amenity-amenity similarity matrix $M_{aa'}$. Colors of the matrix indicate the number of neighborhoods we observe two amenity categories with RCA value above 1.

Figure S9: Network representation of the amenity-amenity similarity matrix $M_{aa'}$. Edges represent non-normalized values of co-concentration in neighborhoods.

6 Amenity complexity rankings

Ranking of all amenity categories (Figure S10) and all neighborhoods by their amenity complexity values (Figure S11).

Figure S10: Amenity categories ranked by their amenity complexity value. Categories are colored by their ubiquity across neighborhoods. Complexity and ubiquity values are normalized to 0-1 scale for visualization purposes.

Figure S11: Neighborhoods of Budapest ranked by their amenity complexity value. Neighborhoods are colored by the diversity of their amenities. Complexity and diversity values are normalized to 0-1 scale for visualization purposes.

7 Centrality of locations in Budapest, Hungary

To identify central locations within the city of Budapest, we measure the average distance of locations from each census tract of the city. More precisely, for neighborhoods we measure the Euclidean distance between the centroid of the focal neighborhood and the centroid of all census tracts and calculate the average distance to reach the neighborhood from any census tracts of the city. For actual amenities, we apply the same procedure and calculate the average distance between the centroid of the focal H3 hexagon and the centroid of all census tracts. For both neighborhoods and amenities, we use the inverse of this average distance (log) normalized to 0-1 scale. Figure S12 illustrates the resulted indicators on the map of Budapest, where higher values are associated with locations around the historic inner city of Pest. Figure S13 presents the distribution of the indicator for neighborhoods and amenities.

Figure S12: Centrality of locations (A) Centrality of neighborhoods on the map of Budapest, Hungary. Centrality is measured as the inverse of the average distance to reach a neighborhood from all the census tracts of Budapest. (B) Centrality of amenities on the map of Budapest, Hungary. Centrality is measured by the inverse average distance to reach an amenity from all the census tracts of Budapest. Areas in blue indicate natural water sources.

We choose this solution to quantify the centrality of locations for several reasons. First, Budapest has a convex shape and it is a clearly monocentric city. The application of the Urban Centrality Index (UCI) proposed by Pereira et al. 2013 to the population distribution between Budapest neighborhoods results in Proximity Index (PI) of 0.999 and UCI of 0.386, indicating a highly centralized structure. Second, we take advantage of the census tract structure. Census tracts are relatively homogeneous in terms of population, but very heterogeneous in terms of area. More specifically, census tracts tend to be smaller around the city center and larger on the outskirts.

Figure S13: Distribution of centrality measures for (A) neighborhoods and (B) amenities. Centrality of locations is defined as the inverse of the average distance to reach the location from all the census tracts of Budapest. Areas in blue indicate natural water sources.

The densely populated inner city, which concentrates a large proportion of census tracts results in many neighborhood-census tract pairs (and amenity-census tract pairs) with shorter distances. As a result, the average value of distances will be high for densely populated central locations. Third, this method allows assigning a unique centrality value to each neighborhood and each H3 hexagon based on their relationship to the common spatial unit of the census tracts. Finally, our metric is universal in the sense that it can be applied to any city of similar shape and structure to identify the centrality of locations, and is less city-specific than measuring the distance to an arbitrary central location chosen based on local knowledge.

Table S5 shows how different measures on centrality of locations affect the relationship between socio-economic diversity of visitors. The regressions are based on the example month of February 2020, exactly like our models in the main text. Model (1) is identical with our preferred model from the main text. Model (2) tests the significance of the distance from the center of mass in Budapest. Model (3) uses distance from the zero kilometer stone as an alternative centrality measure. The zero kilometer stone (or landmark zero sculpture) at Clark Ádám tér is the center of Hungary’s main road network, and road network distances are calculated from here. Model (4) introduces the distance from the center of Budapest defined by Deák Ferenc tér. This square is a public transport hotspot in the heart of the city center. For model (5) we compute the Local Indicator of Spatial Association (LISA) using the local Moran’s I for the number of POIs per neighborhood Anselin 1995. More precisely, we find the largest, statistically significant spatial cluster of neighborhoods in which the number of POIs and the average number of POIs in its surroundings is more similar than would be expected by pure chance Rey, Arribas-Bel, and Wolf 2023. The distance from LISA center variable measures the distance of neighborhoods from the center of the largest statistically significant spatial cluster. The resulting center is near the Nyugati Railway Station, one of the largest railway stations in the city. All the above variables capturing urban centrality are log transferred. As all variables for urban centrality are significant and have the expected sign (except the model using center of mass), Table S5 clearly illustrates that urban centrality is related

to socio-economic mixing.

	Coefficient of variation				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Centrality of location	0.130*** (0.027)				
Distance from center of mass		-0.015 (0.025)			
Distance from zero km stone			-0.151*** (0.019)		
Distance from Deak tér				-0.151*** (0.022)	
Distance from LISA center					-0.163*** (0.023)
Population (log)	-0.053** (0.022)	-0.096*** (0.023)	-0.040** (0.020)	-0.038* (0.021)	-0.038* (0.021)
Nr visitors (log)	0.047 (0.029)	0.099*** (0.029)	0.036 (0.026)	0.034 (0.027)	0.024 (0.027)
Nr POIs (log)	-0.001 (0.023)	0.005 (0.025)	0.004 (0.021)	-0.0001 (0.022)	0.004 (0.022)
Constant	0.424*** (0.056)	0.536*** (0.056)	0.576*** (0.048)	0.583*** (0.049)	0.606*** (0.049)
Observations	186	186	186	186	186
R ²	0.257	0.162	0.376	0.335	0.350
Adjusted R ²	0.241	0.144	0.363	0.321	0.336

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table S5: Controlled correlations between the socio-economic diversity of visitors and different measures on central location of neighborhoods

Table S6 presents how different measures on centrality of locations affect the relationship between socio-economic diversity of visitors and neighborhood complexity. Model (1) is used as a baseline, in which we do not control for the centrality of neighborhoods at all. From model (2) to model (6), we present one by one the measures of location centrality presented earlier. The table shows mixed results. While the distance from the center of mass in Budapest does not influence the diversity of visitors, the distance from infrastructure hubs such as the zero kilometer stone, Deak tér or Nyugati railway station, which is the result of the LISA calculation, have high explanatory power.

Table S7 and Table S8 apply the same logic and setting to amenities. Table S7 shows that measures of centrality of location work the same for amenities as for neighborhoods, and that amenities in more central locations are visited by socio-economically more diverse people. Table S8 presents models in which we also control for amenity complexity. The results are mixed, and unlike at the neighborhood level, amenity complexity is significant even after controlling for distance from Deák tér or for the distance from the LISA center (Nyugati railway station area). These regressions suggest that in addition to the physical centrality of locations, centrality within the transport infrastructure may also influence socio-economic mixing in Budapest, Hungary. This would require further evaluation, as the zero kilometer stone, for example, which has the largest explanatory power in both settings, is only a symbolic center of the Hungarian road network. It does not serve as a meeting point for the local population, nor can it be seen as a melting pot of society. However, a deeper assessment is beyond the scope of this research.

	Coefficient of variation					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Neighborhood complexity	0.172*** (0.034)	0.125*** (0.036)	0.172*** (0.034)	0.028 (0.040)	0.056 (0.041)	0.042 (0.041)
Centrality of location		0.089*** (0.028)				
Distance from center of mass			-0.005 (0.024)			
Distance from zero km stone				-0.140*** (0.025)		
Distance from Deak ter					-0.127*** (0.028)	
Distance from LISA center						-0.144*** (0.029)
Population (log)	-0.075*** (0.021)	-0.050** (0.022)	-0.074*** (0.022)	-0.040** (0.020)	-0.040* (0.021)	-0.039* (0.021)
Nr visitors (log)	0.067** (0.028)	0.039 (0.029)	0.067** (0.028)	0.035 (0.026)	0.033 (0.027)	0.025 (0.027)
Nr POIs (log)	0.013 (0.023)	0.006 (0.023)	0.012 (0.023)	0.005 (0.021)	0.003 (0.022)	0.006 (0.022)
Constant	0.399*** (0.057)	0.363*** (0.057)	0.402*** (0.059)	0.552*** (0.059)	0.533*** (0.062)	0.566*** (0.063)
Observations	186	186	186	186	186	186
R ²	0.265	0.303	0.266	0.378	0.342	0.354
Adjusted R ²	0.249	0.284	0.245	0.361	0.324	0.336

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table S6: Controlled correlations between the socio-economic diversity of visitors, complexity of neighborhoods and alternative measures on central location

	Coefficient of variation				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Centrality of location	0.126*** (0.011)				
Distance from center of mass		-0.011 (0.011)			
Distance from zero km stone			-0.132*** (0.011)		
Distance from Deak ter				-0.115*** (0.010)	
Distance from LISA center					-0.109*** (0.012)
Nr POIs in category (log)	-0.013 (0.009)	-0.021 (0.013)	-0.006 (0.007)	-0.006 (0.007)	-0.010 (0.008)
Nr visitors (log)	0.073*** (0.007)	0.096*** (0.009)	0.053*** (0.006)	0.047*** (0.007)	0.056*** (0.008)
Constant	0.220*** (0.033)	0.313*** (0.051)	0.397*** (0.030)	0.388*** (0.032)	0.387*** (0.034)
Observations	2,742	2,742	2,742	2,742	2,742
R ²	0.102	0.052	0.167	0.143	0.138
Adjusted R ²	0.101	0.051	0.166	0.142	0.137

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table S7: Controlled correlations between the socio-economic diversity of visitors and different measures on central location of amenities

	Coefficient of variation					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Amenity complexity	0.113*** (0.021)	0.069*** (0.016)	0.112*** (0.021)	0.019 (0.015)	0.031** (0.015)	0.046*** (0.014)
Centrality of location		0.116*** (0.011)				
Distance from center of mass			-0.003 (0.011)			
Distance from zero km stone				-0.129*** (0.011)		
Distance from Deak ter					-0.111*** (0.009)	
Distance from LISA center						-0.104*** (0.012)
Nr POIs in category (log)	-0.008 (0.008)	-0.006 (0.007)	-0.008 (0.008)	-0.004 (0.006)	-0.003 (0.007)	-0.006 (0.007)
Nr visitors (log)	0.087*** (0.010)	0.069*** (0.008)	0.086*** (0.010)	0.052*** (0.006)	0.046*** (0.007)	0.054*** (0.008)
Constant	0.216*** (0.034)	0.172*** (0.030)	0.219*** (0.035)	0.381*** (0.032)	0.361*** (0.031)	0.347*** (0.030)
Observations	2,742	2,742	2,742	2,742	2,742	2,742
R ²	0.067	0.108	0.067	0.167	0.144	0.140
Adjusted R ²	0.066	0.106	0.066	0.166	0.143	0.139

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table S8: Controlled correlations between the socio-economic diversity of visitors, amenity complexity and alternative measures on central location

8 Dominant amenity categories of H3 hexagons

The second part of our empirical exercise (section 4.2 Diversity of visitors to complex amenities) connects visitors to actual amenities. This is done by mapping each point of interest (POI) from the Google Places API to a size 10 H3 hexagons (Uber Technologies, Inc. 2022). These hexagons are on average 15.000 m^2 area, which is close to the buffer area of a point with a 70 meter radius. As we use the amenity complexity values calculated for amenity categories (see Equation (6) in the main text) to explain the diversity of visitors to size 10 H3 hexagons, we need to assign a single amenity category to each hexagon with POIs. Figure S14 illustrates that most hexagons only have amenities in a single amenity category, however, hexagons at dense, central locations often contain multiple POIs from different categories.

Figure S14: Number of different amenity categories per size 10 H3 hexagons on the map of Budapest (A) and on the map of the inner city (B). Distribution of different amenity categories per hexagons (C). The colorbar applies for all subplots.

We assign a dominant amenity category for each hexagon based on the local frequency of POIs in amenity categories. Figure S15 visualizes our dominant category selection process. 35.15% of the hexagons have ambiguous amenity category dominance and in these cases we simply choose the first category listed. Table S9 illustrates in comparison to Table 2 of the main text that our key findings are the same in case we focus only on amenities in H3 hexagons with a single amenity category or in case we only consider amenities in H3 hexagons with an unambiguously dominant amenity category.

Figure S15: Illustration of the dominant amenity category selection. Different POIs over the hexagons (A) and the determined hexagon category (b).

	Coefficient of variation	
	Single category (1)	Dominant category (2)
Amenity complexity	0.153** (0.075)	0.080*** (0.021)
Centrality of location	0.061 (0.059)	0.127*** (0.012)
Nr POIs in category (log)	-0.032 (0.024)	-0.010 (0.008)
Nr visitors (log)	0.144*** (0.052)	0.063*** (0.008)
Constant	0.154* (0.080)	0.181*** (0.034)
Observations	151	1,849
R ²	0.091	0.127
Adjusted R ²	0.066	0.125
Note:	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Table S9: Controlled correlations between the diversity of visitors and the complexity of amenities in case we only consider H3 hexagons with (1) a single amenity category or with (2) an unambiguously dominant amenity category

9 Alternative measures on the diversity of visitors to neighborhoods and amenities

Table S10 supports the findings presented in Table 1 of the main text. It uses the same model setting to illustrate the relationship between the diversity of visitors to neighborhoods, neighborhood complexity and urban centrality, but applies different measurements of the dependent variable. Besides the coefficient of variation, the Gini index and the Theil index are used to measure the diversity of visitors and all model version suggest similar connections. Table S11 supplements the findings of Table 2 in the main text in a similar fashion at the level of amenities.

	Coefficient of variation (1)	Gini (2)	Theil (3)
Neighborhood complexity	0.125*** (0.036)	0.088*** (0.018)	0.056*** (0.012)
Centrality of location	0.089*** (0.028)	0.032** (0.014)	0.019* (0.010)
Population (log)	-0.050** (0.022)	-0.026** (0.011)	-0.016** (0.007)
Nr visitors (log)	0.039 (0.029)	0.018 (0.014)	0.011 (0.010)
Nr POIs (log)	0.006 (0.023)	-0.002 (0.011)	-0.002 (0.008)
Constant	0.363*** (0.057)	0.198*** (0.029)	0.068*** (0.019)
Observations	186	186	186
R ²	0.303	0.295	0.266
Adjusted R ²	0.284	0.276	0.246

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Table S10: Controlled correlations between different measures on the diversity of visitors and neighborhood complexity

	Coefficient of variation	Gini	Theil
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Amenity complexity	0.069*** (0.016)	0.035*** (0.007)	0.023*** (0.005)
Centrality of location	0.116*** (0.011)	0.051*** (0.005)	0.029*** (0.003)
Nr POIs in category (log)	-0.006 (0.007)	-0.004 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.002)
Nr visitors (log)	0.069*** (0.008)	0.032*** (0.004)	0.016*** (0.002)
Constant	0.172*** (0.030)	0.100*** (0.014)	0.017* (0.009)
Observations	2,742	2,742	2,742
R ²	0.108	0.115	0.074
Adjusted R ²	0.106	0.114	0.073
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table S11: Controlled correlations between different measures on the diversity of visitors and the complexity of amenities

10 Diversity of non-local visitors to neighborhoods

Table S12 supports the findings presented in Table 1 of the main text, but the models consider only the socio-economic diversity of non-local visitors. This means that we excluded all third place visits to neighborhoods by devices with identified home location inside the same neighborhood. Results are very similar to our main models.

	Coefficient of variation (non-local visitors only)				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Neighborhood complexity		0.134*** (0.035)			0.135*** (0.036)
Amenity diversity			-0.169** (0.074)		-0.183** (0.072)
Avg amenity ubiquity				-0.046 (0.048)	-0.013 (0.049)
Centrality of location	0.113*** (0.026)	0.070** (0.028)	0.113*** (0.026)	0.107*** (0.027)	0.067** (0.028)
Population (log)	-0.043* (0.022)	-0.040* (0.021)	-0.038* (0.022)	-0.038* (0.023)	-0.033 (0.022)
Nr visitors (log)	0.039 (0.029)	0.031 (0.028)	0.047 (0.029)	0.037 (0.029)	0.039 (0.028)
Nr POIs (log)	0.008 (0.023)	0.015 (0.022)	0.061* (0.033)	-0.004 (0.026)	0.070** (0.033)
Constant	0.403*** (0.055)	0.337*** (0.056)	0.330*** (0.063)	0.436*** (0.065)	0.267*** (0.073)
Observations	186	186	186	186	186
R ²	0.231	0.287	0.252	0.235	0.312
Adjusted R ²	0.214	0.268	0.232	0.213	0.285
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01				

Table S12: Controlled correlations between the diversity of non-local visitors and the amenity complexity of neighborhoods

11 Amenity complexity and the diversity of visitors over 24 months

Figure S16 illustrates the relationship between diversity of visitors to neighborhoods and neighborhood complexity over 24 months. The figure shows the coefficients for neighborhood complexity from the regression setting presented in Table 1 model (2) of the main text. It suggests that neighborhood complexity does not have a significant relationship with the diversity of visitors in 6 out of 24 months.

Figure S16: Regression coefficient of neighborhood complexity estimated for 24 months by model (2) of Table 1 in the main text. Different colors indicate different levels of significance.

Figure S17 illustrates the relationship between diversity of visitors to amenities and amenity complexity over 24 months. The figure represents the coefficients for amenity complexity from the regression setting presented in Table 2 model (2) of the main text. It shows that neighborhood complexity does not have a significant relationship to the diversity of visitors in 8 out of 24 months. The differences between the two figures do not allow us to argue for a strong impact of COVID-19 on visitation patterns.

Figure S17: Regression coefficient of amenity complexity estimated for 24 months by model (2) of Table 2 in the main text. Different colors indicate different levels of significance.

12 Instrumental variable approaches to estimate the relationship between neighborhood complexity and diversity of visitors

There are a number of potential unobserved factors that influence both neighborhood complexity and the socio-economic diversity of visitors to neighborhoods, creating a potential endogeneity problem when measuring their relationship. To account for this potential endogeneity, we re-estimate our results presented in Table 1 of the main text using different instrumental variable (IV) approaches (Angrist, Imbens, and Rubin 1996). The IV estimation approach corrects for possible endogeneity in regression settings by using variables (instruments) that do not belong to the explanatory equation. The requirement for this is that IVs are uncorrelated to the dependent variable (at least conditionally on the level of the independent variable) but correlated with the main independent variable (in our case, neighborhood complexity).

Broekel 2019 argues that complexity measures constructed from the spatial distribution of activities are potentially endogenous variables in many spatial research settings. At the international level, Salinas 2021 shows that economic complexity is related to the distance of countries from economic centers, and as a result, complexity indicators show spatial correlation. In the main text we present that our measures of amenity complexity are also connected to the urban centrality of locations. To account for this endogeneity issue we follow Stojkoski, Koch, and Hidalgo 2022 and introduce an IV which is constructed for each neighborhood by taking the average neighborhood complexity of the three neighborhoods with the most similar specialization pattern to the focal neighborhood. The logic behind this IV is that neighborhoods with similar specialization patterns should also have similar neighborhood complexity as the focal neighborhood, but the complexity of the similar neighborhoods should not affect the visitation pattern to the focal neighborhood and should not be connected to other neighborhood specific unobserved characteristics. Table S13 presents the IV regressions alongside the original OLS regression from the main text. The IV estimation reinforces our original finding, however, the coefficient of neighborhood complexity is less significant.

In another IV estimation setting, the historical separation of neighborhoods from Budapest is used as an instrument for neighborhood complexity. The current form of Budapest was only realized in 1950, when 59 municipalities gave up their autonomy and were integrated into the capital. We create a dummy variable for each neighborhood and use it as an IV which takes the value of 1 in case the neighborhood only became part of Budapest in 1950 and 0 otherwise. The rationale behind using this variable as an instrument is that municipalities that were independent before 1950 had an amenity structure organized to serve the independent municipality (e.g. independent local administration, marketplaces, libraries or post offices), while the already integrated municipalities could rely more on the central facilities and services of the capital. Consequently, historical separation of neighborhoods could influence their complexity, but not the socio-economic diversity of visitors to neighborhoods today (beyond its indirect effect through complexity). Table S14 presents the IV regressions using historical separation as an instrument alongside the original OLS regres-

	Coefficient of variation		
	OLS		IV
	(1)	(2)	(3)
Neighborhood complexity	0.125*** (0.036)		0.074* (0.044)
Neighborhood complexity (avg of 3 most similar)		0.050* (0.026)	
Centrality of location	0.089*** (0.028)	0.103*** (0.030)	0.121*** (0.030)
Population (log)	-0.050** (0.022)	-0.055** (0.022)	-0.045** (0.022)
Nr visitors (log)	0.039 (0.029)	0.050* (0.029)	0.036 (0.029)
Nr POIs (log)	0.006 (0.023)	0.002 (0.023)	0.002 (0.023)
Constant	0.363*** (0.057)	0.409*** (0.056)	0.375*** (0.059)
Observations	186	186	186
R ²	0.303	0.273	0.294
Adjusted R ²	0.284	0.253	0.275
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01		

Table S13: Diversity of visitors to neighborhoods and neighborhood complexity: instrumental variable approach using similar specialization patterns

sion from the main text. The IV estimation reinforces our original findings, but the coefficient of neighborhood complexity is less significant. Both of our instruments are statistically valid.

	Coefficient of variation	
	OLS (1)	IV (2)
Neighborhood complexity	0.125*** (0.036)	0.485** (0.209)
Centrality of location	0.089*** (0.028)	-0.004 (0.072)
Population (log)	-0.050** (0.022)	-0.031 (0.028)
Nr visitors (log)	0.039 (0.029)	0.007 (0.038)
Nr POIs (log)	0.006 (0.023)	0.024 (0.030)
Constant	0.363*** (0.057)	0.167 (0.125)
Observations	186	186
R ²	0.303	-0.079
Adjusted R ²	0.284	-0.109
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

Table S14: Diversity of visitors to neighborhoods and neighborhood complexity: instrumental variable approach using historical separation of neighborhoods

13 References

- Aslak, Ulf and Laura Alessandretti (2020). “Infostop: Scalable stop-location detection in multi-user mobility data”. In.
- Chi, Bin et al. (2021). “Shedding new light on residential property price variation in England: A multi-scale exploration”. In: *Environment and Planning B* 48.7, pp. 1895–1911.
- Snijders, Tom A.B. and Roel J. Bosker (2011). *Multilevel Analysis: An Introduction to Basic and Advanced Multilevel Modeling. 2nd Edition*. London, UK: Sage Publishers.
- Hungarian Central Statistical Office (2022). *Regional Atlas*. (Online; accessed on 10 December 2022). URL: https://www.ksh.hu/regionalatlas%5C_administrative%5C_units.
- Hidalgo, César A. (2021). “Economic complexity theory and applications”. In: *Nature Reviews Physics* 3, pp. 92–113.
- Pereira, Rafael Henrique Moraes et al. (2013). “Urban centrality: a simple index”. In: *Geographical Analysis* 45.1, pp. 77–89.
- Anselin, Luc (1995). “Local Indicators of Spatial Association — LISA”. In: *Geographical Analysis* 27.2, pp. 93–115.
- Rey, Sergio, Dani Arribas-Bel, and Levi John Wolf (2023). *Geographical Data Science with Python*. Boca Raton: CRC Press, In press.
- Uber Technologies, Inc. (2022). *H3*. (Online; accessed on 28 November 2022). URL: <https://h3geo.org/>.
- Angrist, Joshua D., Guido W. Imbens, and Donald B. Rubin (1996). “Identification of Causal Effects Using Instrumental Variables”. In: *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 91.434, pp. 444–455.
- Broekel, Tom (2019). “Using structural diversity to measure the complexity of technologies”. In: *PLOS ONE* 14.5, pp. 1–23.
- Salinas, Gonzalo (2021). “Proximity and Horizontal Policies: The Backbone of Export Diversification and Complexity”. In: *IMF Working Paper*, pp. 1–31.
- Stojkoski, Viktor, Philipp Koch, and César A. Hidalgo (2022). “Multidimensional Economic Complexity: How the Geography of Trade, Technology, and Research Explain Inclusive Green Growth”. In.